

VIOLENT OFFENCES AGAINST WOMEN, A CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF ROLE OF VICTIMS IN HIGH PROFILE CRIMINAL CASES: A PERSPECTIVE FROM PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Pakistan, a prosperous, multilingual, cultural, and traditional nation, faces challenges such as women victimization and patriarchal nature, leading to social issues like crime, inequalities, high profile criminal cases against women and gender discrimination, affecting various communities. Crimes against women in Pakistan are deeply rooted, despite the country's Islamic values and high respect for women. These crimes affect not only the woman's future but also the family and society. However, as women are weakest segment of society are easily hunted as a prey by masculine gender and subjected to crime. Through this article such factors like contributory negligence and the role of victims in her victimization, criminal judicial system and role of other social stakeholders will thoroughly be scrutinized by critically examining prior commission of high profile criminal cases against women committed in Pakistan examining social, economic, and psychological life styles of victims and offenders before incidence to find out the actual causes and risk factors that are responsible for women victimization. The main causes of women's victimization include honor killings, acid attacks, forced marriages, sexual harassment, rape, trafficking, poor literacy, lack of awareness, social rights, domestic violence, and contributory negligence. This exploratory research aims to identify factors through doctrinal research, library-based, and extensive study of relevant laws, researches, documents, books, materials, journals, and articles as well as focuses on literature review and high-profile cases to understand the root causes of such reactions. To address these issues, the research suggests providing quality education, reducing victims' contributory negligence, eradicating poverty, challenging patriarchal norms, promoting gender equality, and empowering women, forming district committees, improving policing, legislation reforms, and involving religious scholars and community elders.

INTRODUCTION.

The Women victimization refers to mistreatment, abuse, and discrimination against women due to their gender (Cannon, C. E., & Buttell, F., 2023), affecting their rights, dignity, and well-being in various aspects of life, including education, employment, and healthcare (World Health Organization, 2013). The World Health Organization defines violence as an intentional demonstration of power or physical force to cause harm or deprivation. Violence against women, including domestic, sexual, and intimate partner violence (HRCP, 2020), force marriage etc. is a major public health issue worldwide (Campbell, J. C., Abrahams, N., & Martin, L. 2008). Violence against women is a societal issue involving physical, sexual, psychological, and economic abuse, affecting women across diverse cultural, social, and economic contexts. It is of various kinds i.e. Violence committed with the intent to cause bodily harm or injury is referred to as physical violence (World Health Organization, 2012).

Rape, sexual assault, and harassment are examples of acts of sexual violence against women that are carried out without their consent (Women, V. A., 2021). Emotional abuse that targets women with the intention of manipulating or degrading them includes manipulation, threats, intimidation, and other psychological abuse (García-Moreno, C., Pallitto, C., Devries, K., Stöckl, H., Watts, C., & Abrahams, N., 2013). Limiting a woman's financial options or resources is known as economic violence, and it's frequently used as a way to impose control and power over her (Qureshi, S., 2013). The World Health Organization defines violence as an intentional demonstration of power or physical force to cause harm or deprivation. Violence against women, including domestic violence, sexual, harassment, honour killing and intimate partner violence, is a major public health issue worldwide. It affects one in three women in their lifetimes and their children. A framework utilizing the determinants of violence against women as an analytical unit is offered, and literature addressing the problem and its many theories is evaluated.

Human Right groups have criticized about the poor record of human rights in Pakistan in order to safeguard the rights of women and eradicate and discourage violence which is based on gender in the South Asian countries that ranked 130 out of 189 countries on the list of UN's gender inequality index. It's a somber period for introspection, when we advocate women's rights and defends human rights and look at the statistics and figures on violence against women and girls in Pakistan. It is observed during the last so many decades there was less positivity seen in the transgressions committed against young girls and even women. Pakistan, a prosperous, multilingual, cultural, and traditional nation, faces challenges such as women victimization and patriarchal nature, leading to social issues like

crime, inequalities, and gender discrimination, affecting various communities. Crimes against women are a significant issue in South Asia, with 70-80% of women in Pakistan being victims of domestic violence, honour killings and heinous crimes such as rape, assault, and harassment in public and private places. A large number of instances go unreported because of social stigma, fear of reprisals, and lack of confidence in the legal system, despite the Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (HRCP) stating that thousands of women experience abuse every year. Crimes against women in Pakistan are deeply rooted, despite the country's Islamic values and high respect for women.

The issue of violence against women is grave and has repercussions for individuals, families, communities, and society at large. It is vitally important to address and prevent violence against women for the following reasons:

Human Rights Violated states that the fundamental human rights of women are flagrantly violated by violence against them. Regardless of her age, colour, ethnicity, sexual orientation, or financial situation, every woman has the right to live her life free from violence and fear. However, Effects on Health and Well-Being points out that neglecting the women can have serious physical, psychological, and emotional repercussions that have an adverse effect on their health and overall wellbeing. It may result in mental health conditions like anxiety and depression, physical harm, impairments, or even death. A woman's entire life may be affected by the trauma she endures from such events, which can linger forever.

This research also, highlights root causes and other factors such as contributory negligence, socio-economic factors like education, poverty, and lack of awareness of women's rights, criminal judicial system, corruption, limited facilities, delayed justice, and poor rehabilitation of convicts. It suggests reforms in the criminal justice system, highlighting the need for better investigation, justice delivery, and rehabilitation of convicts. Comprehensive reforms at several levels are required to address the underlying causes of crimes against women in Pakistan. Addressing violence against women is not only a moral imperative but also essential for creating a more just, equal, and peaceful world for everyone. This entails bolstering women's legal protections, enhancing the criminal justice system, raising public understanding of women's rights, and tackling the socioeconomic inequalities that fuel gender-based violence. To build a more secure and just society for women in Pakistan, collaboration between the state, civil society, and the community at large is essential.

The crux of this research thesis revolves around finding out the actual factors, root causes, reasons and the circumstances under which the accused person is attracted / provoked

to commit an offence against the women or whether there are any mitigating circumstances in which the women, herself has contributed towards crime against her. In addition to that it would also be discussed if the women are contributing for any crime against them, then in that circumstances whether the courts are recognizing a defence to that extend pre-existed in the personality of victims before they become hunted by the offenders, and identifying the segments those who could be responsible for such socio-economic and psychological defects that brought the offenders and the victims at a final stage of commission of an offence of heinous nature in Pakistani Society (Rahman, N., Wahid, A. N. M., & Chaudhary, N. U. (2023).

Literature Review

Various authors propose various theories and frameworks to explain violence against women, but no single theory can fully explain the multifactorial nature of women's abuse. In recent years violence against women are increasing day by day irrespective of religion, culture, race and territory. However, the reason behind any domestic and social violence can be complex, multifaceted, and all the factors contributing needs to be considered, it can be financial models expounding domestic violence (DV) within the family unit setting. Domestic Violence (DV) is viewed as an instrument that can be applied capacity to rapid or variance in the conduct of the victim under discussion, “regularly women” or an instrument to expand utility by attaining pleasure from conducting such activities. In any discipline of family unit which are rich changes the circulation of Domestic Violence towards the male culprit. In recent increasing trend DV is categorized as inside dealing models where the bartering “ordinary” shrinks to short and violence (Domestic) is exploited in order to intend that keep up the dominate position within / inside the family unit. (Childress, Gioia, & Campbell, 2018).

The following studies were scrutinize and evaluated in order to find the research gaps and factors that were not incorporated by the earlier researchers in their studies.

Pakistan's political instability has led to inconsistent human rights protection, with abuses occurring with impunity and limited accountability. This paper analyses the country's legal protections and the government's compliance with national and international human rights regulations by using a variety of secondary data sources, including human rights reports, news articles, and legal documents, the paper explores the extent to which the government of Pakistan is fulfilling its obligations under national and international human rights regulations. Key issues include rule of law, economic challenges, corruption, terrorism, women's rights, and freedom of expression. Despite positive developments like counter-

terrorism measures and women's rights laws, significant challenges remain, including failure to hold abusers accountable, suppression of dissent, and discrimination against marginalized groups. (Abdullah, Tampubolon, & Malik, Z., 2023).

In a high profile case of violence against women the killer of Noor Mukadam was convicted to murder and was sentenced to death on the reason for denying marrying the offender (Zahir Jaffer). Pakistan court has convicted, condemned and sentenced a man “Zahir Jaffer” to death for the murder, rape and beheading of a woman “Noor Mukadam” in the capital city of Pakistan, Islamabad, last year. The researcher explains that Violence against women is a global issue affecting millions of women physically, mentally, socially, and economically. The objective of this research was that the Declaration of Violence Against Women (DEVAW) outlines due diligence pillars for prevention, protection, prosecution, and remedy. However, Pakistan's legal system struggles to uphold due diligence standards, resulting in an ineffective redress for victims of self, interpersonal, or communal violence. (Monnoo, I. S. (2024)

Another case of violence against women is that of Murder of Qandeel Baloch. When Qandeel Baloch a female from Punjab was murdered in 2016 by her own brother in the name of honour, the demand of getting justice for her, felt vital and tremendously significant. In this research, the researcher states that the effects of surveillance are rarely consistent since they depend on the bodies doing the looking and the ones are being looked at. Surveillance technologies and techniques repeat patriarchal violence, gender hierarchies, categories, systems of control and discipline, and the "male gaze." This study aims to contextualize feminist research on surveillance by examining gendered surveillance applied to the South Asian context and concentrating on technology-facilitated gender-based violence and surveillance in public and private settings. The objective of the research was to raise more general concerns about violence, public-private divides, and legalistic privacy protections while grounding approaches to surveillance in the lived experiences of marginalized bodies. Another researcher states that the direct cause of Qandeel's murder was spreading and asserting her sexuality online, the visibility and prominence had cost her, “her life”. (Al-Rawhi, S. 2016).

The Acid Survivors Foundation data shows that the number of acid attacks is rising day by day. According to this foundation's estimate, 1,090 acid attacks occurred nationwide between 2007 and 2014 (HRCP, 2015). In Pakistan, there were 55 instances of acid attacks in just one year, 2015. Currently, there are just 17 offenders under arrest. Because there is a dearth of decisive punishment taken against these savage individuals, other perpetrators

remain free to strike innocent victims, primarily women. Because despite committed this horrible crime, they know they will escape punishment.

Women belonging to minority religions are often afraid they will be abducted and the national print and electronic media, together with hundreds of young girls from the Hindu and Christian religions, continue to ignore the mistreatment of women. At least 1,000 Pakistani girls of other religions are being forced into Muslim marriages and compelled to convert to Islam every year, according to a report by the Asian Human Rights Commission.

Women have a key position and status in every society as they form almost society's half capitalization and they are accountable for guidance, nurturing, and reformation of the offspring and succeeding generation of both men and women. The woman can have a role of mother and as per Islamic Ideology it is a saying that, "Paradise lies under the feet of the mother". (Haque, M. M. (2018), (Sardar, R. (2015), (Wheeler, B. Ed. (2002). Women are considered to be an integral part of the society. Phenomenal and dynamic changes all over the world are unable to change the status and fate of women in the society.

As for as a woman is considered, she is born exactly by the same lineage, system and from the same womb: Allah is the creator of this whole universe, the almighty is upon his own choice of blessing someone by granting them a male offspring or a female offspring either male or female is purely upon Allah's the almighty will who is the most beneficial and most merciful. (Qur'an, H. Surah Al-Shura). The Prophet (SAAS) says that the women can be treated as the (equal) sisters of men. A woman in her role can play a role wife/spouse who is considered as a source of affection and comfort for her spouse/husband as he is to her: Allah has created female (wives) among yourself so that you live in comfort and calmness. Also he showers blessings of mercy, love and affection between your hearts so that you lead your life happily. (Qur'an, H. Surah Al-Rum). Another, saying about the women by the Allah the almighty is that, "they are made like a garment to you and you are made like a garment to them". (Qur'an, H. Surah Al-Baqara (2), ayah 187).

Abuse during Police Interrogation, Police-Related Violence, and Law enforcement personnel do not even provide a safe environment for women. Numerous reports of custodian violence including rapes and sexual assaults by police officers occur while police custody. According to a 1992 study, 70% of women in police stations had experienced physical or sexual abuse, and not a single person had been held accountable for such heinous crimes. 41 women experienced abuse while in custody alone in 1999. Of them, just six occurrences were minor in nature; in contrast, 21 cases involved gang-rape of women, and 14 cases involved

physical abuse. At least three examples of women dying as a result of cruel male treatment at the hands of police enforcement were documented in 2000 (Niaz, 2003).

In another article written by the London South Bank University's Arsalan Mujahid Ghouri, titled “*The Women Violence in Pakistan: Evidence from Rural and Urban Areas*” makes the recommendation that the institutional and social structures of the patriarchal order, which oppress and discriminate against women in various ways and eventually turn that oppression into behavioural violence, are the main causes of social violence against women. (Ghouri, A. M., & Abrar, N. (2010). It is implied by Rehman's (2009) research that women in our culture experience prejudice and neglect on all fronts. Together, the two sexes must collaborate in order for males to be successful in ending violence against women. Gender inequality represents a significant issue that is closely linked to violence against women. Even when the wife and husband work, the woman is still responsible for taking care of the home, cooking, cleaning, and other duties. It is entirely the women's responsibility to run the household.

It is not out of place to mention here that there are many authors who have already written many books on the subject matter and it is with discussing some of the authors and their books in this regard. Similarly, Samya Burney in her book *Crime or Custom? Violence against Women in Pakistan* she discusses the cases in which the women were murdered by their family members merely in the ground the she was demanding divorce from her husband. (Burney, S. 1999). The author in the same book states that in Pakistan in every 8 hours a woman has been rapped and almost domestic violence has affected between 70 and 95 percent of women. In another book written by Amnesty International USA namely, *Violence Against Women in the name of Honour* states that the violence against the women are very common in Pakistan and very other women are victim of domestic violence or heinous crimes against them such as rape. (Tare, P. 2012). However, the author criticizes the laws made in the Pakistan and states that the implementations of the laws are not practiced by the law enforcement agencies and courts.

Theoretical / Conceptual Framework

Women victimization is a significant issue in Pakistan, with high-profile cases in recent years. Factors such as Contributory Negligence by the victim in her victimization, socio-economic and psychological factors, the criminal judicial system and the relationship between victim and offender have not been addressed in previous researches. This research aims to highlight these issues and guide policy-making.

Hypothesis

This research believes the validity of misconception regarding the role of victims in their own victimization in the light of available case laws.

Research Methodology

In this research the methodology is an exploratory in its nature as it will suggest finding those socio-economic and psychological factors and other root causes that can lead an offender to react against a victim in whom a victim is contributing through some contributing factors by herself to provoke the predator at an extreme level where the defendant become violent and resulting in an abusive and victimization of plaintiff, and in this way she becomes an easy prey for the defendant. It will be based on doctrinal research. However, Doctrinal methodology is library based and it includes extensive study of relevant laws, researches, documents, books, materials, libraries (E as well as physical), journals and articles etc. Research is main based on literature review connected to the issues and high profile cases.

Research Design

This research is qualitative and primary in nature. It deals with the investigation of the events and data in a systematic manner and is based on library and books. This research is not intended to test any theory rather it is conducted to find out those contributory negligence factors either socio-economic or psychological that are contributing in violent offences against women where a woman is contributing through her own negligence and inviting the offender to become violent against her. It will help in exploring those deficiencies or shortcomings that are not addressed either in investigating process or provision of justice system etc.

Data Collection and Variables of study

The data collected in this research is based on the secondary resources. Secondary data has been collected by the various books, journals, articles written by different authors, professionals and other socialist on the subject of violence offences against women and their victimization especially in high profile cases. Moreover, newspapers and media reports can also be considered to gather secondary data, along with authentic information from international organizations are also part of data.

Conceptual Data Analysis & Results

There are many different and intricate factors that contribute to crimes against women in Pakistan. The strongly rooted patriarchal mind-set in the society, which sees women as inferior to men and rationalizes violence against them, is one of the primary causes. Social standards, religious convictions, and cultural expectations all contribute to the persistence of

this mind-set, which supports gender disparity. The absence of legislative safeguards and enforcement procedures for women is another significant aspect. The current legal framework is frequently insufficient or poorly applied and administered, which allows those who commit acts of violence against women to go unpunished. The prosecution of criminals is further hampered by corruption, ineptitude, and a lack of resources within Pakistan's criminal justice system.

Islam protects the right of women. There is not even a single either direct as well as indirect text or quote in the Islamic Law (Shari'a) is remotely suggested that women exist to be evil (inherently) and impure as established / found in certain distorted faith / creeds that signals attribute lies to God. Indeed, the Prophet (P.B.U.H) said in one of his authentic and reliable hadith that "A believer of Allah is never impure".

The data studied from literature reveals the secrets behind victimization of women is factually deep rooted in irrational communication in between victims of high profile cases and the offender, the factors responsible for culpable motivation are attracting low socio, economic classes and high luxurious life style objectives, coupling with mental instability or social disorder.

The role of victim in her own victimization cannot be ignored one hand and on other side of canvas the responsibility of all stake holders responsible for maintaining social , economic and political order of society is weakened hence sparking high profile crimes ranging from minor to heinous offences against women. In conclusion, it is vital to approach discussions surrounding violence against women with empathy, understanding, and a focus on supporting victims. Victims should not be blamed or held responsible for the harm they have suffered. Instead, society has responsibilities to ensure their well-being and safety.

The societies have developed their particular subject matter when the rule of law has been implemented and followed but in our country, the law enforcement agencies are still struggling to implement the legislation and the verdict of court. No doubt an attempt has been made by the parliamentarians to prevent and discourage the heinous crimes against women but loopholes are available in the same as a result of which the accused persons take advantage of the same and get acquittals which adversely affect the courage and the rights of the women in the society. Furthermore, the cultural norms and customs are huge barriers in developing the laws upon rights of the women and to reduce the crime rate against them. It is not out of place to mention here that in most of the cases the women are being killed are tortured on the basis of the dignity of the family and tribe. Legislation on such cultures and norms are missing in Pakistan.

Recommendations

This research article emphasizes the importance of addressing violence against women with empathy, understanding, and support for victims. It suggests that society has responsibilities to ensure their well-being and safety. It is therefore suggested and recommended that categorically legislation in which such acts have to be discouraged by sentencing death penalties on honour killings. Furthermore, contributory negligence has never been discussed in any legislation in Pakistan before which may be including as mitigating circumstances where the women are at fault. Such as getting into relationship without any Nikkah with a man or handling them as western culture in tribal areas. To fold it, recommendation is also suggested here one falls on the part of government to provide quality education and also provide all the financial and other facilities to remove poverty. On the other hand, the responsibilities also fall on the shoulders of the parents to properly keep a check and balance on the teenagers to avoid any mishap and to reduce the rate of crimes against women and children. Furthermore, the department and the government is also under a responsibility to take all necessary measures such as educating the women on their right on social as well as on print media at district and village level. Similarly, a committee must be formed in every tehsil chaired by notable women of the area empowering her to take actions against the crimes against women and report the same to police. Furthermore, she may also give the power to assist the victim all sort of medical facilities including the scientific evidences such as DNA etc. to make the case stronger against the accused.

The preventive measures for providing effective security and sense of safety to women could be implemented by public awareness, gender studies, social work and reforms in the Criminal Justice System of Pakistan. The data has shown that in major crimes the role of modern digital cyber space was also one of the key aspects of providing motivation to the offenders for commission of violence and aggression against women. The cyberspace space may be secured by effective legislation for cyber security. Improvement in policing by establishing separate police stations for women and establishing well settled forensic mechanism of evidence collection. Further in nexus to same religious and molar up gradation of thoughts could be done with help of relevant religious scholars and family elders of community all across country. Pakistan's government and progressive political parties should prioritize women's education and re-education for boys and men to avoid physical, sexual, or emotional abuse. The media can be a powerful tool in creating awareness about women's rights, but it often portrays women as enjoyable for men. The government should focus on enhancing police and judiciary agencies, creating more women's police stations, and establishing family courts and women's courts. Religious leaders and academics can act as

anchors, planning training programs and pressuring the Pakistani government to take appropriate action. International organizations like the UN and Amnesty International can take note of incidents of violence against women and exert pressure on the government to take appropriate action. To develop policies and programs against women's violence, all available resources and supportive sectors of society must be mobilized and used effectively. While additional research is needed to enhance the framework, it has the potential to motivate individuals to take action by assisting men, women, public health experts, and policy and decision-makers in understanding the dynamics of violence against women. This could lead to a cultural revolution that better lives for women. Policy makers, professionals, law enforcement agencies, and scholars should play a role in eradicating these evils by digging down the root causes against the victims.

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Quranic Surahs.

(Qur'an, H. Surah Al-Baqara (2), ayah 187)

(Qur'an, H. Surah Al-Rum (30), ayah 21)

(Qur'an, H. Surah Al-Shura (42), ayah 49)